

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКАЯ ЦЕННОСТЬ ПРОТЕОМА СЛЮНЫ. МИНИ-ОБЗОР

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THE DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF THE SALIVA PROTEOME. MINI REVIEW

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Поиск новых, быстрых и малоинвазивных методов диагностики заболеваний, как полости рта, так и общих заболеваний различной этиологии и их внедрение в практическое здравоохранение по-прежнему являются приоритетными в области медицины. Среди известных методов анализа биологических жидкостей особое место занимает исследование слюны. Анализ ротовой жидкости обладает высоким потенциалом в скрининге различных заболеваний, поскольку содержит широкий спектр органических и неорганических соединений. Значительное количество исследований было посвящено изучению количественного и качественного состава ротовой жидкости, а также изучению биомаркеров слюны, однако изучение протеома слюны находится на стадии накопления данных. Отсутствие стандартизации в отборе образцов и методах анализа, а также малоизученные физиологические и биохимические параметры ротовой жидкости препятствуют внедрению достижений в области изучения протеома слюны в диагностическую практику. Решение этих задач позволит использовать ротовую жидкость в качестве биологической среды, как для выявления заболеваний, так и для прогнозирования их течения.

ABSTRACT

The search for new, fast and minimally invasive methods of diagnosing diseases of both the oral cavity and general diseases of various etiologies and their introduction into practical healthcare is still a priority in the field of medicine. Among the well-known methods of analysis of biological fluids, a special place is occupied by the study of saliva. Oral fluid analysis has a high potential in the screening of various diseases, since it contains a wide range of organic and non-organic compounds. A significant number of studies have been devoted to the study of the quantitative and qualitative composition of oral fluid, as well as the study of saliva biomarkers, but the study of the saliva proteome is at the stage of data accumulation. The lack of standardization in the collection of samples and analysis methods, as well as poorly studied physiological and biochemical parameters of oral fluid, prevents the introduction of advances in the study of the saliva proteome into diagnostic practice. The solution of these tasks will allow the oral fluid to be used as a biological medium for both the detection of diseases and the prognosis of their course.

Ключевые слова: ротовая жидкость, биохимические маркеры, неинвазивная диагностика, экспресс-диагностика, протеом.

Keywords: oral fluid, biochemical markers, noninvasive diagnostics, express diagnostics, proteome.

Interest in rapid and less invasive diagnostic tests has been growing in a geometric progression in recent decades. Currently, the study of oral fluid is of interest to most researchers. Saliva is a viscous liquid with a pH of 5.8 - 7.6, the composition of which varies depending on the rate of its secretion. About 99 - 99.4% of saliva

is water, 1 - 0.6% - mineral and organic substances. The inorganic components of saliva are in the form of macronutrients dissolved in it by anions - chlorides, phosphates, bicarbonates, rhodanides, iodides, bromides, sulfates, as well as Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} cations. Trace elements are determined in saliva: Fe, Si, Mn, Ni, Li,

Zn, Cd, Pb, Li, etc. All mineral macro and microelements are found both in the form of simple ions and in the composition of compounds - salts, proteins and chelates. The formation and excretion of saliva into the oral cavity is carried out by three pairs of large salivary glands (near-ear, sublingual and submandibular) and many small salivary glands. However, it is worth distinguishing between saliva and "oral fluid" or "mixed saliva". The oral fluid or mixed saliva, in addition to the secretion of the salivary glands, contains epithelial cells, leukocytes, microorganisms, food residues and is an important factor for maintaining their homeostasis [1].

Mixed saliva is an environment in which the organs of the oral cavity are located throughout life and is the most important factor for maintaining their homeostasis [2]. Undoubtedly, an integral part of the homeostasis of the oral cavity is the quantitative and qualitative (trace elements, proteins, immunoglobulins) composition of the oral fluid, which indicates local immunity. The main and most important properties of oral fluid are mechanical, immunological and antibacterial activity. Indicators of mixed saliva are closely related to the physiological state of the body and the pathology of the dental system. The presence of concomitant pathology, as well as taking medications, leads to a violation of its physico-chemical and metabolic parameters, which directly affects the development of diseases of the hard tissues of the teeth, periodontal tissues, oral mucosa [3-5].

Even in the early Middle Ages, alchemist-healers tried to use saliva to make a diagnosis, and Avicenna and his followers generally believed that saliva and blood had the same origin [6].

However, oral fluid analysis became more widely used only in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries, due to the emergence of new biological methods for protein isolation and purification, the development of modern sensitive amplification methods, improved methods for the selection and processing of saliva samples, as well as the development of metagenomic analysis [7].

For a long time, numerous studies have been aimed at studying the morphological and physiological features of the structure and functioning of the salivary glands. As a result of numerous studies, the quantitative and qualitative composition of saliva was determined, the values of the ratio of electrolytes, proteins, enzymes in it were determined, and its crystal properties were studied [8]. There is evidence of changes in the parameters of oral fluid with age, so during the period from newborn to the period of senile age, there is a decrease in the amount of daily saliva production, which is associated with age-related changes in the morphology of the salivary glands. According to various studies, based on the studied parameters of oral fluid, namely immunoglobulins IgA, IgM, IgG and secretory IgA, pro-inflammatory factors (interleukin-13, interleukin-6, interleukin- 8, tumor necrosis factor- α), it is noted that in elderly and in senile age, the production of immune defense markers decreases, which leads to an increase in the risk of developing autoimmune and inflammatory processes in the oral cavity [9].

In this connection, it became possible, based on the analysis of oral fluid, to diagnose various diseases not only in the oral cavity, such as caries [10],[11], periodontitis [12], diseases of the oral mucosa [13], but also a number of systemic diseases: autoimmune diseases [14], [15], viral [16], [17], [18], bacterial diseases [19], cardiovascular diseases [20], diabetes mellitus, Alzheimer's disease [22], neuropsychiatric disorders [23], as well as oncological diseases [24], [25].

Conclusion

Thus, the analysis of oral fluid has a high potential in the screening of various diseases, since it contains a wide range of organic and inorganic compounds. The study of the composition and properties of oral fluid, as well as the study of saliva biomarkers, makes it possible in some cases to determine not only the state of the body as a whole and the tissues of the oral cavity, but also in some cases to predict the course of the disease. A significant number of studies have been devoted to the study of the quantitative and qualitative composition of oral fluid, as well as the study of saliva biomarkers, but the study of the saliva proteome is at the stage of data accumulation. The lack of standardization in the collection of samples and analysis methods, as well as poorly studied physiological and biochemical parameters of oral fluid, prevents the introduction of advances in the study of the saliva proteome into diagnostic practice. The solution of these tasks will allow the use of oral fluid as an express test, which can become an alternative to invasive technologies for early diagnosis, preparation of a treatment plan and prognosis of the course of the disease.

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